

Shaping the Festival Perception by Exploring Urban Commons in the City

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Abstract:- Festivals constitute connections between culture of celebration and places. Festivals their unique places which can play a major role in the place identity. This research is based on considering culture of celebration which is a powerful urban tool to create collective place identity through urban commons and city image. Such festivals are being the spectacles for the image of the city which perceived as kinetic city. In the static city there are only consideration of architectural components. However, there is no designated public spaces for celebration. This research tries to learn and analyses festival locations in the kinetic and its Implementation in static city.

The analysis of the interviews narrates how different visitors of the festival perceive the city in general as well as describes the possible effects of the celebration to their perception. Qualitative data is connected with theories of festival culture of celebration and experience of the place. The research tries to understand the role of the festivals and concludes that urban commons in the city can create the festival identity in the cities.

Keywords:- Place Identity, Festival Perception, Placemaking, Urban Commons, City Image.

I. INTRODUCTION

"सण' जीवनातील सांस्कृतिक पैलूंचा उत्सव." ("‘Festivals’ A celebration of cultural aspects of life.”)

Festivals bring people together to celebrate their culture and rituals. It is the most significant activity which gives a sense of enjoyment and relaxation to humans. Festival creates the identity of the city due to its culture of celebration. The festival identity of a place becomes a unique character that provides opportunities to accomplish urban spaces in the city and which further enhances the urban image of the city. Such recreational spaces can act as the most preferred locations to attract people to celebrate, investors as it also becomes a tourist destination. Festival

culture always reorient itself according to changing scenarios of development. This research attempts to enable social, economic and environmental sustainability through congruences with the festival culture.

India is largely decorative with different festival cultures and having their physical cultural landscape. As per research, 82 festivals are celebrated in all states of India. Out of those, there are four typology of festivals celebration in public spaces i.e., mass gathering (Ganesh Utsav, Shiv Jayanti, etc), concert or stage events (Navratri, Diwali, etc.), lakefront (idol immersion) and market fairs (Jatra). As per perception analysis, 71% of people think that these festivals do not have designated identical locations. But with their interest 90% people feel that such festival spaces can have relaxation time and interactive places during the event time.

This research attempts to highlight the way with which place identity is affected by festivals and the culture of the neighborhood. Considering their temporary entity at specific places it aims at structuring an interface between place identity and festivals. Main assumption of this study is that festivals that are unique to their places can have the power to continue year by year to the senses that are identified with the places in the conscious mind.

➤ Research questions

- How do the events in public spaces change the way we perceive the city?
- How can urban design tools evaluate understanding of festivals?
- How is the relationship between festivals and people to become the identity of the city?
- What are the characteristics of the place identity which influences the perception of humans with respect to festivals?
- The interaction of festivals and every day space through urban commons can come up with the perception that can enhance the traditional and cultural identity of the place is the hypothesis of research.

Fig 1 Significance of festival (Source: Author)

In today’s scenario, the festival place is seen as a recreational activity where people used to pay for gathering and celebrating. On the basis of this, the focus of this research research has been defined by two main considerations. The first is the popularity of festivals and their effects on communities. Festivals and culture of celebration have numerous definitions and typologies. They also have different meanings for different type of communities. The second is to create a relationship between the urban design aspect and festivals emergent in the everyday realm.

The research is a study that can be significant as looking with the consideration of people’s perception to the festivals and involving the place identity with festivals. Every such place is becoming an entertainment feature for the neighborhood residents where they can gather and have a sense of enjoyment. By enhancing the identity of such an area through analyzing festival perception, it becomes the designated festival place in the city.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Preservation of disappearing of traditional activities from the public spaces is the highest demand for the future generation. Public open spaces creation can be a phenomenon of cultural tradition, but develops in contact with other cultures. Therefore, the cultural activities in all its forms must be preserved, enhanced and handed on to future generations as a record of human experience and aspirations, so as to foster creativity in all its diversity.

India is characterized by physical and visual contradictions that are the combination of the cultural activities and urban landscapes. In other words, the economic, social or culture of cities may occupy different spaces on a temporary basis, the everyday spaces where economic and cultural struggles are articulated. These common spaces have been largely excluded from the

cultural discourses on globalization, which focus on elite domains of production in the city (Mehrotra, 2008).

Today, Indian cities are composed of two components. The first is the **Static City**, built of only architectural components and more of permanent materials, it is comprehended as a two-dimensional entity on conventional city maps. The second is the **Kinetic City**, incomprehensible as a two-dimensional entity, it is perceived as a city in motion, a three-dimensional incremental development where festivals are being the spectacles for the image of the city. It is temporary in nature and occasionally events which change the entire nature of any specific area. The Kinetic City presents a compelling vision that potentially allows us to better understand the blurred lines of contemporary urbanism and the changing roles of people and spaces in urban society (Mehrotra, 2008). The increasing concentrations. Global flows have inequalities and spatial divisions between social classes which affect the architecture or urbanism of equality.

➤ *Festival celebration in the city*

Urbanized city, a city engaged with daily routine, increasing their economic growth. People living there, do they really feel fascinating to celebrate their festivals, their rituals in public places? After resettling from native place, they perceive something lost in their culture. Therefore, such places in the city may give them an opportunity to celebrate festivals and preserve cultural identity. In the past, festival celebrations started in front yard, back yard or common neighborhood public spaces. Eventually, due to its culture of celebration and popularity it becomes the place identity to that area. In the urbanized city, it lacks such common spaces and due to which people acquire part of the road area or any vacant area for celebration. Though, this area is not a designated festival place. This research assumes that festival places can not only make an identical or designated place for celebration but also it can act as an image of the city.

➤ *Experience of Place*

Religion may act as a powerful tool to create place identity which forms the unique identity of the experience of place. This research aimed at the importance of people and their experience to the places. However, it depends upon

how the social interaction between people and environment can be measured. The design of the proposed urbanism should be responsive to local and the background structure. The creation of places should be attachments between people and places.

III. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Fig 2 Theoretical Framework (Source: Author)

➤ *Urban Placemaking*

As both an overarching idea and a hands-on approach for improving a neighborhood, city, or region, placemaking inspires people to collectively reimagine and reinvent public spaces as the heart of every community. Strengthening the connection between people and the places they share, placemaking refers to a collaborative process by which we can shape our public realm in order to maximize shared value. More than just promoting better urban design, placemaking facilitates creative patterns of use, paying particular attention to the physical, cultural, and social identities that define a place and support its ongoing evolution.

With community-based participation at its center, an effective placemaking process capitalizes on a local community's assets, inspiration, and potential, and it results in the creation of quality public spaces that contribute to people's health, happiness, and wellbeing.

These types of spaces have huge potential of improving the place and creating a stronger urban fabric of

the city. Reclaiming the dead spaces by intervening could solve the perception of these spaces and thereby create better shared spaces by increasing the imagination and comfort. Each area has its own unique characters, therefore activities that are distinctively unique to that area should be allowed to expand in order to create places with identity rather than only traditional planning.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research has more concentration on how culture can be the most important factor of any developing city. It can be implemented in the open spaces, where people can experience the authenticity of the city. Based on this concept, the research will be more of qualitative analysis. It should reflect how culturally the city is important to the world. At the same time, it is also quantitative research as the relationship between festival, people and neighborhood cultural places has been critically analyzed.

Fig 3 Research methodology (Source: Author)

Collecting data for the analysis of perception gathered from the unknown participants of the festival in the different city. Here, concern was whether people are willing to express their feelings during the festival period in their city. Also, whether their city has such designated places for festivals. All this data is collected through the online questionnaire. The aim to gather data about people's perception supported the decision of festival places as important for the city as it has unique character and most importantly this survey gives the informants more time to think about what they remember about the festival in public places.

For quantitative data analysis, it is necessary to map festivity in identical cultural places in the city. Based on this, their detailed mapping has been made with consideration of the physical pattern of celebration. This research commences with an overview of literature on culture of cities set by who, bringing the attention on authentic public spaces in current urban areas. Proceeding from this, an extensive literature on the framework of kinetic city and static city is applied as an introductory setting to provide a base for understanding the need of festivals in an urban environment.

To support such research various cases are analyzed. Those cases are also categorized into four types. First is the nuclear & polynuclear festival location, which has designated places for festival celebration or eventually some

places are identical for such celebrations. Second is the temple precinct festival location, areas that have authentic or religious ways of celebration. Third is city center festival locations such as lakes, open spaces and streets, designated festival platforms which can also act as happening places throughout the year.

V. CONCLUSION

This conclusion follows from the fact that the analysis and discussions made throughout the study provided a base to defend the effect of festivals in place identity. Festivals have been presented as dynamic place elements that enable people to encourage memory, attachment and meaning to the places. To take this inference one step further and make the discussion more concrete in terms of urban commons design.

The broad implication of the present research is that gathering data about people's perception supported the decision of festival places as important for the city as it has unique character. Proceeding from this, an extensive literature on the framework of kinetic city and static city is applied as an introductory setting to provide a base for understanding the need of festivals in an urban environment.

This research states that festivals' perceptions can enhance the traditional and cultural identity of the place. Therefore, this research focuses on reimagining and

exploring the festival and its culture of celebration of a kinetic (Urbanized) city, to shaping the festival perception in the static (urge of urbanization) city.

After abundant research on the topic of festival perception in the city can achieve a greater impact developing better cities and communities, with improved socio-cultural, legible and varied conditions towards identity and making a small difference to the world. This research concludes that the festival perception through urban commons in the city have the power to strengthen the festival identity in the cities.

REFERENCES

➤ Book References

- [1]. Doyle, J. (2015). *The creative city*. Gower publishing limited .
- [2]. Gehl, J. (2013). *Cities of people* . Island press .
- [3]. Mehrotra, R. (2016). *The emergent urbanism in Mumbai, Kinetic city* . ORO editions.

➤ Website References

- [4]. (n.d.). *History Of Lalbaug | Educo India*. From <https://www.educoindia.org/history-of-lalbaug.php>
- [5]. *Case study of kankaria lake, Ahmedabad*. (2016, December 8). From J.Architecture: <https://amitjaviya.blogspot.com/2016/12/blog-post.html>
- [6]. De, B., & Davi. (2010, November 5). *Celebrating group and place identity: A case study of a new regional festival*. From Taylor & Francis Online: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14616680110055439>
- [7]. Every day is a celebration. (2011, December 3). *Times of India*. From <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/every-day-is-a-celebration/articleshow/10472963.cms>
- [8]. *Exclusive: Balkrishna Doshi Unveils the Details of the Revitalisation of Bhadra Fort*. (2016, May 2). From World Architecture Community: https://worldarchitecture.org/articles/cevzg/exclusive_balkrishna_doshi_unveils_the_details_of_the_revitalisation_of_bhadra_fort.html
- [9]. Gehl, J. (2010). *Cities for people*. Google books. From https://books.google.co.in/books?id=IBNJoNILqQcC&printsec=frontcover&source=gbs_ge_summary_r&cad=#v=onepage&q&f=false
- [10]. Gosavi, Y. (2022). *Festival places* . From Google form : https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1Ofn2LDINXw4EU_nQZIMmn-tUYm-iXPfJNEvtm5Rs-ZLw/edit
- [11]. Magdalena, M. (2017). *The role of an urban festival in public space: case study of the Light Move Festival in Łódź*. cta Universitatis Lodziensis. Folia Geographica Socio-Oeconomica. From https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259742788_Culture_Urban_Strategy_A_case_study_of_a_major_festival

- [12]. Neil, J. W. (2004). *Urban Planning and Cultural Identity*. Routledge, London. From https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Urban_Planning_and_Cultural_Identity/18uAAgAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&printsec=frontcover
- [13]. Parmar, M. (2015, October 19). *October 2015*. From between architecture and Urbanism | Manoj Parmar: <https://messmatrix.blogspot.com/2015/10/>
- [14]. Pillai, P., & Nadkar, P. (2016, September 4). The God of Big Things | Lifestyle News. *The Indian Express*. From <https://indianexpress.com/article/lifestyle/art-and-culture/the-god-of-big-things/>
- [15]. Sawahney, T. (2018). *Art and Culture to play a pivotal*. Transforming Urban India ed.
- [16]. SRFDCL. (n.d.). *Background - Sabarmati riverfront* . From Reconnecting ahmedabad to its river : <https://sabarmatiriverfront.com/background/>
- [17]. *Sursagar Lake Vadodara - Renovation Plan 2018*. (2018, January 2). From YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OkJI8119D4c>
- [18]. *The Cultures of Cities*. (1991). Wiley. From <https://www.wiley.com/en-us/The+Cultures+of+Cities-p-9781557864376>
- [19]. Tiwari, M. (n.d.). *Redefining public realm at Sursagar lake precincts Vadodara*. From Academia.edu: https://www.academia.edu/32899949/Redefining_public_realm_at_Sursagar_lake_precincts_Vadodara
- [20]. *UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity*. (n.d.). From United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia: <https://en.unesco.org/about-us/legal-affairs/unesco-universal-declaration-cultural-diversity/>
- [21]. Whyte, W. (1993). *The Social Life of Small Urban Spaces*. From Informal Science: https://www.informalscience.org/sites/default/files/VS_A-a0a1v6-a_5730.pdf

➤ Article References

- [22]. Widiastuti, I. (2008). *PHENOMENON OF DISTRICT ART IN KALA GHODA FESTIVAL, MUMBAI*. From Research Gate: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303793003>
- [23]. *What is Placemaking?* (n.d.). From Project for Public Spaces: <https://www.pps.org/article/what-is-placemaking>
- [24]. Stevens. (2012). *URBAN FESTIVALS AND LOCAL SOCIAL SPACE accepted manuscript*. From CiteSeerX: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.833.969&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- [25]. Singh, S. (2013). A Case of Kankaria Lakefront Redevelopment Project. *Urban Design redefining Cultural Spaces*. From <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/255719747>
- [26]. Mehrotra, R. (2008). Negotiating the Static and Kinetic Cities: The Emergent Urbanism of Mumbai. *Other Cities, Other Worlds*(Duke University Press), 205 - 218. From https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv11cw83k?turn_away=true